

ARCHITECTURE

KARABAGH MONUMENTS

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Abstract

This article is dedicated to the monuments of the Karabakh region, which has a special place in the architectural history of Azerbaijan. It should be noted that although most of these architectural pearls located in different regions of Azerbaijan have come down to our time, those related to Karabakh have been subjected to significant destruction from time to time, especially in the last thirty years, as a result of Armenian aggression, and many of them have been appropriated by them. Among them, there are Christian-type religious architectural monuments from the period of ancient Caucasian Albania and the Early Middle Ages. In the Middle Ages, numerous civil buildings were built in different corners of Karabakh along with mosques, tombs and castles. Among them, the buildings created by architect Karbalai Safikhan Karabakhi stand out. Of course, since these buildings with the Karabakh address are directly related to the local people living here due to their shape, masonry technology and aesthetic capacity, it is impossible to hide their real address - who owns them. On the other hand, the fact that the Armenians, who erected a monument in Agareh district in honor of the 150th anniversary of their relocation from Iran to Karabakh in 1978, is only regrettable and laughable.

Keywords: architecture, monument, mosque, minaret, inscription, dome, synthesis.

It is no coincidence that architecture, being the main component of Azerbaijani art, which has a very ancient history and rich artistic traditions, has significant importance in many ways. Thus, the presence of its old examples in the territory of the country first of all indicates the antiquity of the people who settled here. On the other hand, such monuments with different functions and forms indicate the breadth of imagination of local architects and the high performance culture of artists. There are various menhirs and bonfires from ancient times, as well as the ancient Kish temple, Amaras monastery, circular temple in Lekit village, Gum basilica, Agoglan temple, Khudaveng monastery complex, Diribaba tomb, etc. it is possible to be sure of it in the example of religious purpose, as well as different buildings such as Maiden's Castle, Askeran Castle, Shirvanshahlar Palace, Shamakhi Juma Mosque, Shahbulag Castle and Mardakan Castle. For your information, although most of these architectural pearls located in different regions of Azerbaijan have come down to our time, those related to Karabakh have been subjected to considerable destruction from time to time, especially

in the last thirty years, as a result of Armenian aggression, and many of them have been appropriated by them. Among them, there are Christian-type religious architectural monuments from the period of ancient Caucasian Albania and the Early Middle Ages. Of course, since those buildings are directly related to the local people living here due to their shape, masonry technology and aesthetic capacity, it is impossible to hide their real address - who they belong to. On the other hand, it is only regrettable and laughable that the Armenians who erected a monument in Agara region in honor of the 150th anniversary of their relocation from Iran to Karabakh in 1978...

When talking about the ancient monuments of Karabakh, first of all, we need to remember the religious ancient buildings of Caucasian Albania and Albanian principalities that existed in the territory of present-day Azerbaijan. In other words, the monuments built at that time constitute a certain period of Azerbaijan's architectural history. One such monument that preserves the history of Caucasian Albania is the basilica-type Agoglan temple, located in the Lachin region and belonging to the 5th-6th centuries.

Agoglan temple. V-VI centuries (VI-VII centuries). Lachin.

The village of the same name and this temple, located on the bank of the river, are also known as "Agoglan Piri" which is related to legends among the people, and it is primarily due to its use as a place of faith since ancient times. It was converted into a church and functioned as a monastery. Let's add that although restoration works are being carried out here, the renewal of the building by preserving its original foundation made it a remarkable monument of that period.

Studies show that the monument, which has a rectangular shape, has gone through three stages of construction over time. The main architectural feature of the monastery is its division into three naves by means of stone columns. It is undeniable that the addition of a horseshoe apse in the mihrab part of the middle nave of the monument gives its interior a special beauty. Completing the side naves lined up along the length of the building with rooms located on the sides of the mihrab increased its functionality even more. In addition, the fact that the side nave is semicircular, the central nave has an axial roof, and the mihrab has an arched

shape has given the general view of the interior a tangible elegance. During the occupation of Azerbaijani lands by Armenians, they made certain purposeful changes in its general capacity. Therefore, it will take some time to restore it to its previous appearance

Let us say here that the renaissance period of Christian architecture in Azerbaijan begins in the 12th century. Many religious buildings, including various churches, monasteries and temples, were built between the 12th and 14th centuries. In this sense, Khudaveng (1214), Ganjasar (1216-1238), Khatraveng (1204) and other monastery complexes can be mentioned.

The Khudavang monastery in Kalabajar district is considered one of the monuments that keep traces of ancient history. The history of the essay coincides with the arrival of Christian missionaries to Caucasian Germany - the first centuries of our era. This magnificent building is located in the village of the same name in the region. Khudavang Monastery includes more than ten religious and secular buildings of various sizes and designs.

Khudaveng monastery complex. VIII-IX centuries. Kalbajar

It should be noted that these buildings were built in different historical periods by the order and patronage of individual persons. The oldest building here is the ancient basilica dating back to the 8th-9th centuries. Arzu Khatun church with cathedral status was built in 1214. The Khudaveng monastery, which is the religious center of the Principality of the Albanian Cross, also houses the residence of the Albanian bishop and the center of religious propaganda. In the 13th century, the center was further updated and given a magnificent appearance by adding a monastery and other various buildings by the family of Bahram, the son of Khachin Prince Big Hasan, a representative of the Mehranyar dynasty. However, as in the case of the Agoghlan temple, during the occupation of the territory, our villains tried to Armenianize this monument and made some changes to it.

The Ganjasar monastery complex (XIII century) located in the territory of Vangli village of Kalbajar district was one of the magnificent and remarkable buildings of its time due to its artistic and technical characteristics. For this reason, this monastery is known as the religious and cultural center of Caucasian Albania. This complex consists of a church and an entrance hall, as well as various auxiliary buildings. In addition, the location of numerous cells and various buildings in the vicinity of its northern and southern walls gives the complex its uniqueness. The fact that the building is surrounded by castle walls with two gates on the southern and western sides is also an architectural feature that distinguishes it from others. Like other religious monuments of Azerbaijan, additions were made to it by Armenians during the occupation of the country's territory, and considerable damage was done to its general appearance. Let us say here that over time, numerous mosques, mausoleums and tombs related to Islam have been built in the territory of Karabakh. Before talking about these monuments, it should be noted that urban planning has been widely developed here. In this sense, the works carried out in Beylagan should be especially mentioned. Historical sources mention that it was formed as a city in the XI-XII centuries. Unfortunately, the city was almost destroyed after the Mongol invasion in the 13th century. However, as a result of the archaeological excavations carried out here, it has been possible to restore the previous landscape of the city, and the locations of the city's fortress walls, inner fortress, palaces and kiosks, palaces and mosques, narrow streets and squares have been identified. During the excavations, it was determined that beyond the walls of the castle, Bayirshaher, where artists worked, numerous mausoleums, as well as an architectural complex known as Mil-Minare, etc. buildings existed.

While talking about the medieval buildings of Karabakh, we need to mention the Shykhbabali tomb (1272) located in Babı village of Fuzuli region. This monument, which has an interesting structure - octagonal appearance, covered with a dome at the top, is one of the few buildings that preserves the architectural aesthetics of the thirteenth century, and is also of historical and cultural importance due to its unique solution. First of all, this peculiarity manifests itself in the fact that it is single-layered, unlike the double-layered domes in

Azerbaijan. On the whole, the fact that it has such a simple construction determines its lightness, but it has reduced the resistance of the monument to various atmospheric pressures.

The tomb in Ahmadallar village of that region is similar to the monument we talked about. Despite its external similarity, the dome of this building is covered with two layers of stone, which distinguishes it from the monument we are comparing. In addition, the Ahmedallar tomb is distinguished by the entrance to it in the form of an ornamented portal. Since the monument's inscription was destroyed, it is difficult to tell the exact date of its construction. However, it can be assumed that the second tomb was built at the end of the second half of the 13th century.

Unlike the Ahmedallar tomb, the construction date of another tomb located in Barda, one of the capitals of Caucasian Albania, is known. In the inscriptions of the monument, it is mentioned that it was built in 1322 by Banna Alhafiz Ayyub oglu. The total height of the monument, which consists of a cylindrical body and a cone-shaped dome, is fourteen meters, and its diameter is ten meters. This structure, consisting of an underground crypt and an above-ground tower, belongs to the group of tower-like tombs. The area of the monument from the pedestal to the frieze at the top is covered by a pattern made of baked bricks and bricks with turquoise tiles on the face. Writing the word "Allah" more than two hundred times across the surface of the combined masonry of those bricks can be considered a successful discovery of the architect. For this reason, the building is more popular among people as "Allah-Al-lah" tomb.

The presence of the Mir Ali tomb, built in the XIV century, in the territory of Fuzuli region confirms once again that those places are rich in architectural monuments. The building, located in the village of Ashaghi Veysalli, consists of a narrow cylindrical body rising on a three-step platform and a conical dome that completes it. The arched arched portal that surrounds the entrance door on its northern facade has given the building its uniqueness. The general structure of the above-ground and underground parts of the monument, which has survived to our time in good condition, gives reason to say that it belongs to the constellation-type buildings.

Belonging to that period, another tomb distinguished by its originality is located in Khachinturbatli village of Aghdam district. The building erected in 1314 is the product of master Shahbanzar's imagination. Unlike other buildings of that period, this monument is distinguished by its rich interior design. Thus, the interior of the tomb, which has an octagonal shape, is decorated with patterns of carving and decoration.

One of the notable buildings in Khojaly Mounds near Aghdam is the white stone tomb. Researchers attribute it to the group of tower tombs due to its artistic and technical indicators. The 14th century monument has other features that make it stand out from the rest. In addition to its dodecagonal shape, its entrance is decorated with carved ornaments.

Although the name of the architects of many buildings built in Karabakh is not known, it is known that several eye-catching monuments of the region

were created by the local architect Karbalai Safikhan Karabakhi (1817-1910). The works of the artist, who is rightfully considered the most prominent representative

of the Karabakh school of architecture and who can effectively use local architectural traditions, adorn the cities of Shusha, Fuzuli, Aghdam and Barda.

Aghdam Friday Mosque. 1868-1870. Architect Karbalayi Safikhan Karabagi

Although his creativity is made up of buildings of various purposes, among them religious buildings, especially mosques, occupy a wider place. In this sense, the Lower Govhar Agha Mosque (1874-1875), Upper Govhar Agha Mosque (1883), Saatli Mosque (1883), Haji Yusif, Mamay, Julfalar and Cölgala neighborhood mosques in Shusha city (19th century); Friday Mosque in Aghdam (1868-1870); In Fuzuli, the village mosques of Haji Alakbar (1889), Horadiz (1891-1908) and Goçehmadli (1906) can be mentioned. In the general aesthetics of these religious buildings, in addition to loyalty to local architectural traditions, the national spirit is also felt.

Despite this wealth, the Lower Govhar Agha and Yukhari Govhar Agha mosques built by him in Shusha

are notable for their unique artistic features. It should be noted that the architect built both mosques by the order of Ibrahimkhalil Khan's daughter Govhar Agha.

The Lower Govhar Agha Mosque, located in the Gapan Square of Shusha, known as the "Conservatory of the Caucasus", was built earlier than the other one. Nevertheless, both mosques have almost the same dimensions. However, Ashagi Govhar Agha Mosque is notable for its main facade with three arched balconies. Let's add that the central arch of the mosque is distinguished by its axial shape compared to the sides. The fact that its minarets are connected to the southern facade also distinguishes it from the Yukhari Govhar Agha Mosque, which was built later.

Yukhari Govhar Agha Mosque

If we have to analyze the architectural features of each of them, then we should say that the prayer hall of Ashagi Govhar Agha Mosque is covered with a gable and five domes. The appearance of the mosque mihrab, decorated with stalactites, gives the interior of the building a special beauty. It is also undeniable that the elongated balconies reserved for women on the sides of the second floor enrich the overall artistic capacity of the mosque. In addition to emphasizing these positive aspects, it is necessary to say that the building suffered considerable damage during the occupation

Safikhan Karabakh of Karbala is considered to be the author of the modern double minaret appearance of this mosque, which underwent restoration and reconstruction several times in the eighteenth century. The decoration of the minarets of this mosque by Mir Mohsen Nawab, a famous artist of that time, also distinguishes this building from its predecessor. The entrance of the mosque is solved by a semi-circular stone arch, giving its facade a noticeable playfulness. Let's add that together with the arch of the built portico, three arches rising along the height of the two-story building brought playfulness to the overall image. The verses of the "Quran" written on the arches of the balcony, reminding of the decorative strip, determined the uniqueness of the artistic capacity of the building. Along with two domes with a diameter of five meters, which are part of the design of the roof of the mosque, the brick

minarets decorated with colored stones and divided into three parts along the height are among the features that characterize the building.

The second Juma mosque of Shusha city, built on the basis of similar architecture-planning principles - the main - northern facade part of Ashagi Govhar Agha mosque, is designed with three arched arcaded balconies. However, unlike the Upper Govhar Agha Mosque, the middle arch of this mosque is built in an axial shape compared to the semi-circular arches located on the sides. Another difference is in the minarets of the mosque. Thus, while the minarets of the Upper Govhar Agha Mosque cover the main facade, the minarets of the Lower Govhar Agha Mosque cover the southern facade - the Gapan Square. At the same time, the artistic design of the minarets did not include geometrical ornaments, only vegetable motifs and the motif of repeating the word "Allah" were used. It should be noted that the interior of both mosques is decorated with ornaments reflecting the Islamic religion and wall paintings with various plots. Unfortunately, after the occupation of the city of Shusha, the interior of both mosques was brutally destroyed by the Armenians, and the interior design of the mosque has almost completely lost its previous appearance

One of the famous architect's interesting creative works is Juma mosque in Aghdam. During the occupation of the city, in exchange for the razing of the city to

the ground, that mosque has reached our days in a partially intact state, despite the fact that cattle and pigs were kept here. The reason for this was that the invaders used it as a strategic object and observed the surrounding area from its minarets. The mosque was built in the second half of the twentieth century, more precisely, in 1868-1870. The square-shaped prayer hall of the mosque, which has a square plan, is given its uniqueness by the four columns placed here. The general shape, which is outwardly equal-sided, caused the three deep niches forming its eastern and western sides to give the interior a rectangular appearance. It is also quite visible that the high mihrab on the south wall of the prayer hall in the building became the dominant feature of the interior. The balcony-shaped area on the sides is intended for the worship of women. It is obvious that the minarets in the corners of the northern facade of the mosque give grandeur to the building.

When talking about the architecture of the Karabakh region, we also need to mention the civil constructions built in Shusha. In other words, two madrasahs, six kanvansaras, two castles, fortress walls, and numerous neighborhood springs can be noted for local architectural features built here. In this sense, we would like to visit Karim Bey Mehmandarov and Iskander

Rustamov in the city. So, these buildings are also valuable for the murals inside them. It is also possible to observe the synthesis of arts in those buildings. Let us add that at the time of these monumental paintings, Usta Gambar Karabagi, Mir Mohsen Navvab, etc. have worked

In conclusion, it should be said that the monuments with different functions in Karabakh are valuable as part of our national architectural history. Thus, it is possible to trace the artistic and technical features of the architecture of Karabakh, including Azerbaijan, which has a centuries-old history, in their example.

References

1. Abdulrahimov R., Abdullayeva N. Architecture of the early capitalist period (XIX-early XX centuries). Volume IV. Baku, "East-West", 2013. 349 p.
2. Efendi R. Azerbaijani art. Baku, "East-West", 2007. 397 p.
3. Aliyev Z., Khalilov A. Azerbaijani art. Encyclopedia. Volumes II-III. Baku, "Letterpress", 2011. 200 p.
4. Amanzade R. Azerbaijani architecture at the beginning of XV-XIX centuries. Volume III. Baku, "East-West", 2013. 228 p.

PIETRO DELLA VALLE'S JOURNEY TO AZERBAIJAN AND PERSIA IN 1614 - 1626 (ARCHITECTURAL NOTES)

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ПУТЕШЕСТВИЕ ПЬЕТРО ДЕЛЛА ВАЛЛЕ В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАН И ПЕРСИЮ В 1614 -1626 ГГ. (АРХИТЕКТУРНЫЕ ЗАМЕТКИ)

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Abstract

The close interaction of the artistic cultures of the East and the West, the inclusion of Azerbaijan in the world system of the Silk Road since ancient times is an outstanding achievement of the epochs. The inexhaustible desire of Western European travelers to visit the unexplored corners of the East dates back to ancient times. Among them Italians have a significant place, including Giosafat Barbaro, Ambrogio Contarini, Piero Querini, Archangelo Lambertini, Diego de urra Conca, Veccetti brothers, etc. "Walking far to the East" (V. V. Bartold) the Italians reached as far as the headquarters of the Mongol khans in Karakorum, to China and Southeast Asia. Italian merchants who mastered the "roads of spices and jewels" became emissaries of world trade. Among the most famous researchers-Italian travelers of the Middle Ages (missionaries, merchants, ambassadors, etc.) a special place belongs to Pietro Della Valle (1586-1652), a man of the widest palette of talents as a scholar, linguist, and book collector. Pietro Della Valle, whom Viaqqi called the best researcher of the Renaissance period of the early 17th century between Istanbul and Goa, a person who left a bright mark in the study of the architectural art of the Safavid period. A considerable place in his memoirs was filled by letters from Iran (Persia), an epistolary heritage, an invaluable source of knowledge about its political, social and administrative life, military and legal aspects, intellectual and cultural sphere. An essential place in these belongs to architecture with descriptions and sketches of cities, architectural complexes and monumental buildings, as well as magnificent parks and gardens. This is where the author stops, outlining only some of the monuments visited and described by Pietro Della Valle.